

Intimate Partner Cyberviolence and the Dark Tetrad

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Relationships between Intimate Partner Cyberviolence and Dark Tetrad Traits: A Moderation Effect of Gender

Bojana M. Dinić^{a*}, Danica Radosavljević^b, and Christie Tetreault^c

^a*Department of Psychology, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia;* ^b*Department for Execution of Non-Institutional Sanctions and Measures, Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, Republic of Serbia;* ^c*School of Psychology, National University of Ireland Galway, Galway, Ireland (now University of Galway)*

While previous studies have shown significant effects of dark traits on intimate partner violence, little is known about their effect on intimate partner cyberviolence (IPCV), and findings are rather mixed. The aim of this research was to explore the relationships between the Dark Tetrad traits and forms of IPCV, using a multidimensional approach, as well as examining the moderation effect of gender on these associations. The sample included 293 heterosexual adults from Serbia. The results showed that all Dark Tetrad traits had significant correlations with threatening behaviors as a direct form of IPCV.

Furthermore, primary psychopathy explained the use of devices to monitor partners and threatening (or actual) posting of embarrassing photos of a partner, which are combinations of indirect, invasive, and direct forms of IPCV. Secondary psychopathy explained all other forms of IPCV that were more intrusive and excessive. Narcissistic admiration contributed to explaining threatening behaviors, and narcissistic rivalry explained checking behaviors. Moreover, the results showed that sadism and Machiavellianism in men, and sadism and narcissistic rivalry in women, were associated with certain IPCV forms. These results contribute to a better understanding of the complex relationships between dispositional factors of antisocial behaviors (dark traits) and various forms of IPCV.

Keywords: cyber dating abuse; controlling partner; cyberstalking, Dark Triad; gender differences

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Introduction

Intimate partner violence (IPV) is a health concern throughout the world, and it can include a variety of abusive behaviors (physical violence, psychological violence, and/or sexual violence), inflicted by a current or former romantic partner or spouse (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2022). Although there are numerous theories of IPV, this research will focus on personality theories. Among them, Holtzworth-Munroe et al. (2000) offered a typology of male batterers: family only, dysphoric/borderline, low-level antisocial, and generally violent/antisocial. Among these types, the latter showed the highest levels of marital and general violence, both in the past year and average yearly adult general violence, involvement in criminal activity, psychopathy, and substance use and abuse (Holtzworth-Munroe et al., 2000), suggesting people with this typology would be high risk for IPV perpetration. Some research has showed that the typology of female perpetrators is similar to that of male offenders (e.g., Babcock et al., 2007). Numerous studies have investigated the risk factors for the perpetration of IPV from the domain of personality characteristics (e.g., Spencer et al., 2020; Tetreault et al., 2021). Results of a meta-analysis (Collison & Lynam, 2021) showed that personality disorders, as well as psychopathy as the subclinical trait, were significantly positively related to the perpetration of various types of IPV.

In the last 10 years, researchers have been discovering that with technological advancements, technology is being utilized to abuse intimate partners, called intimate partner cyberviolence (IPCV). Technology facilitates new forms of violence and abuse, such as cyberstalking, surveillance through digital devices, and the distribution of intimate photos and videos without consent. Perpetrators can exploit digital platforms to manipulate, harass, or coerce their partners, often blurring the lines between physical and online environment. IPCV often reflects broader power imbalances within intimate relationships, where perpetrators use technology to assert dominance and control over their partners (e.g., Gilbar et al., 2022). Unlike IPV, little is known about the role of personality traits in the explanation of IPCV, especially the so-called dark traits, which are subclinical traits that increase the susceptibility to engaging in antisocial behavior and poor interpersonal functioning (e.g., Chabrol et al., 2009; Dinić et al., 2020b; Pineda et al., 2022). In this study, we focused on relationships between Dark Tetrad traits

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and various forms of IPCV perpetration. Additionally, we explored the potential moderating role of gender in these relationships.

Intimate Partner Cyberviolence

IPCV is a technology-mediated form of IPV that occurs between two individuals who are currently, or have been, intimately involved with each other (e.g., Gilbar et al., 2022). IPCV perpetration behaviors include using applications to track a partner's location, monitoring a partner's online activities, exerting control over a partner's online communications, or engaging in excessive unwanted communication (e.g., texting multiple times per hour) with a partner, and taking or posting intimate photos of a partner without a partner's consent (i.e., revenge porn). With each new addition or enhancement in technology, there are additional ways for partners to perpetrate IPCV (Flach & Deslandes, 2019; Taylor & Xia, 2018).

A meta-analysis showed positive large effect sizes for the correlation between IPCV and in various types of in-person IPV perpetration, with higher correlation between IPCV perpetration and psychological in-person IPV perpetration compared to sexual and physical/stalking (Gilbar et al., 2022). In the same meta-analysis, it was also found that all types of IPV victimization highly correlated with IPCV victimization. Despite the similarities between the IPV and IPCV, they have different prevalence rates. While 13-20% of people experienced some form of in-person IPV victimization in a previous year (Archer, 2000; Dutton et al., 2017), IPCV victimization ranges from 50% (Borrajo et al., 2015) to 92% (Cavalcanti & Coutinho, 2019). The prevalence of cyber control perpetration was 82%, while of cyberaggression was 10.6% with a tendency towards repeated abuse over time (Borrajo et al., 2015). In a recent study by Fissel et al. (2021), 28% of the participants experienced at least one IPCV behavior in the previous six months. The most commonly experienced forms of IPCV were controlling and monitoring, followed by online aggression; while sexual coercion (e.g., asking for explicit images) and financial control (e.g., monitoring where a credit card was used) were the least experienced (Fissel et al., 2021). Similarly, in Maftai and Dănilă (2023) 34% of the participants perpetrated and 25% experienced at least one IPCV behavior in the previous six months. Thus, both victimization and perpetration of IPCV appear to be much more prevalent than in-person IPV, making it potentially the most experienced and perpetrated form of abuse within an intimate relationship.

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Furthermore, there are different risk factors and outcomes for IPV and IPCV. For example, it has been found that being a victim of abuse of power and control, which is more similar to IPCV motivations, was more predictive of poorer health outcomes compared to physical IPV (Coker et al., 2002). Also, some studies found that psychopathy was more correlated to face-to-face psychological abuse compared to cyber psychological abuse (Bui & Pasalich, 2021). Thus, it is important to understand the determinants of IPCV perpetration and its various forms, as they could differ from in-person IPV. While IPV and IPCV have some overlap, they also have unique risk factors that need to be teased apart.

Gender Differences in Intimate Partner Cyberviolence

A meta-analysis showed that there were no significant gender differences between the average levels of different types of IPCV victimization and perpetration (Gilbar et al., 2022). However, there are gender differences when specific forms of IPCV were explored. For example, women showed a higher prevalence for checking calls and email histories, making excessive phone calls, and monitoring their partner's social network, while men used devices (GPS and hidden cameras) to monitor their partners more frequently (Brem et al., 2021; Burke et al., 2011). Overall, women were more likely to cyberstalk their long-term partners (March et al., 2023) and to engage in both invasive (e.g., logging into a partner's accounts, checking phone history) and passive forms of cyberstalking (e.g., checking a partner's social media account, monitoring behaviors through social media) compared to men (March et al., 2022). Other research found that women with average or high romantic jealousy and alcohol misuse were positively related to cyber controlling partner behaviors, which was not the case for men (Brem et al., 2021). These results indicate that relationships between risk factors and IPCV could have gender specific differences, suggesting a potential moderation role of gender. Thus, it is important to consider a multidimensional approach to IPCV, as only investigating overall IPCV could hide gender differences across specific forms.

Dark Triad/Tetrad Traits and Intimate Partner Cyberviolence

Dark traits are related to various antisocial outcomes, including online aggression (Moor & Anderson, 2019). The Dark Triad represents a constellation of three socially aversive traits: Machiavellianism, subclinical narcissism, and subclinical psychopathy (Paulhus & Williams, 2002). Machiavellianism is characterized by a cynical worldview and manipulative interpersonal style while narcissism is characterized by a superior self-view, grandiosity, and entitlement. In

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this research, the contemporary Narcissism Admiration and Rivalry Concept (NARC; Back et al., 2013) of grandiose narcissism was used, which distinguishes narcissistic admiration as assertive self-enhancement (social potency based on a grandiose self) from antagonistic self-protection aspects of narcissism (social conflict based on devaluation of others and hostile aggression), respectively. Widely used model of psychopathy contain two main dimensions – primary (lack of empathy, remorse, and guilt, high manipulation and selfishness) and secondary psychopathy (lack of behavioral control and tendency towards antisocial behaviors, e.g., Levenson et al., 1999). Sadism was added as the fourth trait, forming the Dark Tetrad (Chabrol et al., 2009). Sadism includes the enjoyment of other people’s suffering and pain (O’Meara et al., 2011), and it has been shown to explain antisocial behavior beyond the Dark Triad traits (Chabrol et al., 2009).

Previous studies confirmed that Dark Triad traits were related to different forms of IPV perpetration (Bui & Pasalich, 2021; Delicato, 2021; Tetreault et al., 2021). When it came to the specific forms, some studies showed that among Dark Triad traits, only psychopathy significantly predicted stalking behavior for both men and women (Delicato, 2021). However, there are still gaps in the exploration of the relationships between the dark traits and IPCV perpetration. For example, Bhogal and Wallace (2021) did not find associations between the Dark Triad and the perpetration of overall IPCV. However, when exploring more specific forms of IPCV, other studies showed mixed results regarding the role of specific dark traits. Nevertheless, there is a consistent finding that dark traits, or some of them, correlate to certain forms of IPCV. In a systematic review, it was shown that all the Dark Triad traits were correlated to non-consensual sexting (portmanteau of sex texting) and technology-facilitated sexual violence (specifically, image-based sexual abuse or “revenge porn”), but only psychopathy was a significant predictor in the regression model (Moor & Anderson, 2019). This demonstrates that while the dark traits has overlap, each trait has unique attributes and behavior for IPCV.

Previous research has also showed that psychopathy was the dominant predictor of direct cyberaggression perpetration (i.e., writing an insult on social media); narcissism of perpetration of cyber controlling behaviors; sadism of direct cyberaggression victimization; while Machiavellianism showed negative contributions, especially to the perpetration of direct cyberaggression (Pineda et al., 2022). In a study by Smoker and March (2017), all Dark Tetrad traits were found to be positively associated with intimate partner cyberstalking with sadism and

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Machiavellianism showing higher contributions compared to narcissism and psychopathy. In another study, cyberstalking was positively related to psychopathy, narcissism, and sadism, but not to Machiavellianism (March et al., 2022).

However, in a follow-up study (March et al., 2023), the Dark Tetrad traits, except for narcissism, were significant predictors of cyberstalking in short-term relationships and all Dark Tetrad traits were significant predictors of cyberstalking in long-term relationships. In another recent study, in which different forms of cyberstalking behaviors were explored, the results showed that all Dark Tetrad traits correlated with passive IPCV (e.g., checking online accounts and monitoring a partner's behavior through social media), while invasive cyberstalking (e.g., logging into a partner's account, checking a partner's messages and phone/computer history without their knowing) was only correlated with psychopathy for both genders (March et al., 2022). Duplicitous cyberstalking (e.g., posing as someone else over social media, using a fake account, catfishing) was correlated with psychopathy (for both genders), narcissism (for women), and sadism (for women; March et al., 2022). Furthermore, gender moderated the associations between dark traits and cyberstalking with narcissism and sadism being significant predictors for women and psychopathy being a significant predictor for men (March et al., 2022).

The inconsistent findings could be a result of a unidimensional approach to dark traits, as well as to IPCV. Therefore, there is a need for a more nuanced approach in which the multidimensionality of both will be considered to gain better insight into the effect of dark traits on specific IPCV forms. In a few studies where a multidimensional approach was used, results showed that not all subdimensions of dark traits had a significant relationship with IPCV. For example, although not all dark traits were included, Branson and March (2021) employed a multidimensional approach in investigating narcissism and psychopathy. They found that only vulnerable narcissism (characterized by negative affect, hypersensitivity, and fragile self-esteem) and secondary psychopathy (erratic lifestyle and antisocial behavior) were significant predictors of IPCV (Branson & March, 2021). In addition, March et al. (2023) found that vulnerable narcissism, but not grandiose narcissism, was a significant and positive predictor of perpetrating cyber dating abuse. These findings underscore the necessity for a multidimensional approach not only to IPCV but also to dark traits, considering their subtraits. In this study, we apply a multidimensional approach to both dark traits and IPCV, which has not been done in the extant research.

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The Current Study

Previous research has suggested that there are significant positive associations between the Dark Tetrad traits and IPCV perpetration (e.g., Pineda et al., 2022). However, results regarding the predictive role of the dark traits were inconsistent when specific forms of IPCV were explored as well as when the multidimensionality of dark traits was neglected (March et al., 2022; Moor & Anderson, 2019; Smoker & March, 2017). Considering that cyber controlling was the most frequent IPCV form and considering its significant association to the in-person IPV (Borrajo et al., 2015), it is important to further explore the effects of the Dark Tetrad traits on various forms of controlling behaviors, in addition to various IPCV forms. In line with previous studies (Branson & March, 2021; March et al., 2022; Pineda et al., 2022), **H1** is: all the Dark Tetrad traits, especially sadism, psychopathy, and narcissism, will be positively and significantly associated with the various forms of IPCV perpetration.

In order to get better insight into these associations, a multidimensional approach to the dark traits (i.e., primary and secondary psychopathy and narcissistic admiration and rivalry) was applied. This approach could help explain the inconsistent results of previous research, as they mostly analyzed data with a unidimensional approach to the dark traits. Since different dimensions of the dark traits, such as psychopathy, obtained different associations with IPCV perpetration (e.g., Branson & March, 2021), and in some cases with IPV perpetration in opposite directions (see Robertson et al., 2020 for a review), it is important to consider the multidimensional constellation of the dark traits in exploring their effects. Therefore, **H2** is: among dark traits, secondary psychopathy and narcissistic rivalry, as the antagonistic aspect of narcissism, were expected to be the main correlates of IPCV forms.

Furthermore, previous studies showed that women had a higher prevalence of specific IPCV forms, such as perpetrating cyber controlling partner behavior (Brem et al., 2021; Burke et al., 2011) and that gender moderated the relations between some of the risk factors and these behaviors (Brem et al., 2021; March et al., 2022, 2023). Therefore, **H3** is: gender should moderate the associations between the Dark Tetrad traits and IPCV forms. We expected to find higher associations between these variables in women compared to in men, i.e., that dark traits in women would be more prominent risk factors for IPCV perpetration.

Materials and Methods

Participants and Procedure

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Power analysis performed in G*Power 3.1.9.7. (Faul et al., 2007) for linear multiple regression (fixed model and R^2 deviation from zero) and 6 tested predictors, medium effect size, $\alpha = .05$, and $\beta = .95$, resulted in a required 146 total sample size. Our study was more than sufficiently powered with a total sample of 293 heterosexual adults from the general population in Serbia (188 or 64.2% identified as women, with 1 participant not indicating their gender), aged between 18 and 68 years ($M = 29.27$, $SD = 10.09$) were included in the analyses. All participants indicated they were White. Men and women did not differ in age ($t[289] = 0.43$, $p = .667$), educational level (Mann-Whitney $U = 9761.00$, $p = .981$), or relationship status ($\chi^2(1) = 3.42$, $p = .065$). For completed education level, 13.7% had completed primary or secondary school, 36.9% participants were currently university students, 3.4% had completed higher professional school, 42.3% had completed a bachelor's or master's degree, and 3.8% had completed a PhD or postgraduate studies. Concerning employment status, 54.9% were currently employed, 39.2% were unemployed, and 5.8% were volunteers. The majority of the participants reported they were in a relationship (54.6%) or married (21.8%), 20.8% were single, and 2.7% were divorced.

The sample was a convenience sample, recruited by using a snowball sampling method with posting recruitment announcements on Facebook (e.g., on authors' Facebook accounts and Facebook groups and pages related to mental health themes) and blogs related to mental health themes (from April 9th to September 13th 2020). The inclusion criteria were that participants were ≥ 18 and have had intimate relationships. Data were collected through Google Forms and approximately 20min was needed for completion. Participants completed the measures voluntarily and anonymously, providing informed consent at the beginning of the measures. All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committee and with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards. The study was approved by the Ethical Committee of the Department of Psychology, Faculty of Philosophy in Novi Sad, Serbia.

Measures

Controlling Partners Inventory (CPI)

The CPI (Burke et al., 2011) consists of 18 items on a 5-point frequency scale (1 = *never* to 5 = *4 or more times*) to measure different forms of IPCV, such as monitoring, controlling, and harassing behavior of intimate partners. Participants were asked to rate the frequency of

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perpetration of each behavior towards their intimate partners in their lifetime and in their current or past relationships. Originally, the authors proposed a 4-factor structure: a) the use of devices (camera, GPS, SpyWare) to monitor a partner and posting or threatening to post inappropriate photos of a partner (8 items, e.g., “Use spy ware to monitor my partner’s activities.” and “Made embarrassing, insulting, threatening wall posts.”); b) excessive communication through phone calls, texts, or emails (4 items, e.g., “Sent excessive number of texts to partners.”); c) threatening through phone calls, texts, or emails (3 items, e.g., “Sent threatening text to partner.”); and d) checking behaviors, such as checking email and call histories, using a password to check-up on a partner (3 items, e.g., “Checked partner’s cell call histories.”). The original items were translated into Serbian by Danica Radosavljević and Bojana M. Dinić and back-translated by a professional lector in order to check the original meaning was retained. Since this is the first use of the Serbian adaptation of the CPI, its model was tested and results confirmed the proposed structure with modification of two items [WLSM $\chi^2(129) = 169.63, p = .01, CFI = .95, TLI = .94, RMSEA = .02$, see Appendix for details].

Machiavellianism Scale (Mach IV)

Mach IV (Christie & Geis, 1970, for the Serbian adaptation see Međedović & Petrović, 2015) consists of 20 items on a 5-point Likert scale (from 1 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*) measuring Machiavellianism characteristics, such as cynicism, manipulative tactics, and pragmatic morality (e.g., “Never tell anyone the real reason you did something unless it is useful to do so.”).

Levenson Self-Report Psychopathy Scale (LSRP)

LSRP (Levenson et al., 1995, for the Serbian adaptation see Dinić et al., 2020a) consists of 26 items on a 5-point Likert scale (from 1 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*) measuring primary psychopathy (16 items, regarding callousness, manipulation, exploitation, e.g., “For me, what’s right is whatever I can get away with.”) and secondary psychopathy (10 items, regarding impulsivity, boredom and frustration intolerance, lack of perseverance, e.g., “When I get frustrated, I often ‘let off steam’ by blowing my top.”).

Narcissistic Admiration and Rivalry Questionnaire (NARQ)

NARQ (Back et al., 2013, for the Serbian adaptation see Dinić & Jovanović, 2021) consists of 18 items (from 1 = *not agree at all* to 6 = *agree completely*), measuring two facets of grandiose narcissism - narcissistic admiration (9 items on assertive aspects of narcissism driven by self-

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enhancement, e.g., “I show others how special I am.”) and narcissistic rivalry (9 items on antagonistic aspects of narcissism driven by self-defense, e.g., “I want my rivals to fail.”).

Short Sadistic Impulse Scale (SSIS)

The SSIS (O'Meara et al., 2011; for the Serbian adaptation see Dinić et al., 2020a) contains 10 items on a 5-point Likert scale (from 1 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*) measuring sadism and the enjoyment of hurting others (e.g., “Hurting people would be exciting”).

For all scales, a higher scores indicates a higher presence of the personality trait. Descriptives for average scores and Cronbach's alpha reliabilities for the scales' scores are presented in Table 1.

Data Analysis

There was a violation of normality for all CPI scales, narcissistic rivalry, and sadism with all scales showing skewness and kurtosis higher than ± 1.5 (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019). Therefore, scores on these scales were normalized by *rankit* transformation. Next, descriptives, alpha reliabilities, test of differences between genders (through *t*-tests), and zero-order correlations among all variables were calculated. Zero-order correlations between the dark traits and CPI scales were also calculated for men and women, separately. Then, differences in correlations between men and women were analyzed with the Fisher's *Z* test. For testing the moderation effect of gender, four hierarchical multiple regression analyses were conducted (one for each CPI scale as a criterion) with the Dark Tetrad traits as predictors in the first step, gender in the second step, and their interactions in the third step. All analyses were performed in IBM SPSS v.27, while the *Z* test was calculated via an online calculator (<http://vassarstats.net/rdiff.html>) as well as Cohen's *d* (<https://lbecker.uccs.edu>).

Results

Preliminary Analyses

Considering the frequency of IPCV forms, only 6.5% of the participants indicated they perpetrated at least one of the described behaviors on the devices and photos scale, 27.6% on the excessive communication scale, 4.6% on threatening behaviors scale, and 53.9% on checking behaviors scale. Detailed frequency data by gender are given in the Appendix.

There were small, significant gender differences on the scores on using devices and photos for IPCV perpetration ($t(290) = 2.53, p = .012, d = 0.30$) and checking behaviors scales ($t(290) = -3.16, p = .002, d = 0.37$) with men showing more use of devices for monitoring partners and

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posting inappropriate photos of their partner and women showing more checking behaviors. There were no gender differences in scores on excessive communication ($t(290) = -0.29, p = .77, d = 0.03$) or threatening behaviors scales ($t(290) = 0.13, p = .90, d = 0.02$). Gender differences were significant but small on Machiavellianism ($t(290) = 2.96, p = .003, d = 0.35$), narcissistic rivalry ($t(290) = 2.64, p = .003, d = 0.31$), and sadism ($t(290) = 3.63, p < .001, d = 0.43$), while they were medium gender differences on primary psychopathy ($t(290) = 5.20, p < .001, d = 0.61$), with men scoring higher. There were no significant differences in secondary psychopathy ($t(290) = -0.14, p = .89, d = 0.02$) and narcissistic admiration ($t(290) = -.44, p = .66, d = 0.05$).

All dark traits were significantly and positively correlated with threatening behaviors, and, among the dark traits, narcissistic rivalry was the strongest correlate (Table 1). Moreover, secondary psychopathy showed significant positive correlations with all IPCV forms, except for the use of devices for monitoring partners and posting inappropriate photos of a partner. Primary psychopathy and sadism showed additional significant positive correlation with the latter.

TABLE 1

There were significant differences in zero-order correlations between sadism and checking behaviors ($Z = 2.02, p = .04$) with this correlation being higher among men (Table 2). Additionally, the correlation between narcissistic rivalry and threatening behaviors was higher in women ($Z = -2.15, p = .03$). There were no other significant gender differences.

TABLE 2

Moderation Analyses

The results of hierarchical multiple regression analyses showed that, in the first step, the Dark Tetrad traits had a significant contribution in the explained variance of all IPCV forms, ranging from 7% (devices and photos) to 13% (checking behaviors, see Table 3). Secondary psychopathy showed significant positive contributions in the explanation of all IPCV forms, except for the use of devices and photos. In contrast, primary psychopathy was a positive predictor of the use of devices and photos. Narcissistic admiration was a significant predictor of threatening behaviors and narcissistic rivalry of checking behaviors, while Machiavellianism and sadism did not have

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significant contributions. In the second step, secondary psychopathy remained a significant predictor of excessive communication, and both secondary psychopathy and narcissistic admiration were predictors of threatening behaviors. Gender showed a significant contribution only in explaining checking behaviors. Although the third step showed a significant contribution only in explaining threatening behaviors, there were some significant interactions in explaining specific forms of IPCV. For instance, the interaction between gender and sadism was significant in explaining the use of devices for tracking the partner and photos for threatening them with the correlation between sadism and this form of IPCV being significant only among men (see Table 2). In contrast, the same interaction was significant in explaining checking behaviors but with a significant correlation between sadism and this form of IPCV only among women. Furthermore, gender moderated the relationships between Machiavellianism and threatening behaviors with this relationship being higher in men, and between narcissistic rivalry and threatening behaviors with this relationship being significant only among women.

TABLE 3

Discussion

The aim of this study was to investigate the relationships between the Dark Tetrad traits and IPCV with a multidimensional approach with the additional exploration of the moderation role of gender differences in these associations. As predicted and in line with previous research (Branson & March, 2021; March et al., 2022; Pineda et al., 2022), all dark traits showed positive correlations with IPCV forms. These gender differences are the most obvious in the relationships with threatening behaviors, as a direct and more damaging form of IPCV. Among the dark traits, narcissistic rivalry showed somewhat higher correlations with all IPCV forms. This result could reflect the antagonistic aspect as the core characteristic (Dinić et al., 2023).

However, due to the partialization of common variance, results of the regression analysis could give us better insight into the unique contribution of each trait. For example, secondary psychopathy emerged as a significant predictor of all IPCV forms in the first step of the regression analyses, except for the use of devices and photos. Additionally, secondary psychopathy was the only significant predictor of excessive communication. The associations between the secondary psychopathy and excessive communication and checking behaviors could

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be explained by impulsivity and reactivity as the unique characteristics captured by secondary psychopathy (Levenson et al., 1995). These forms of IPCV are more intrusive, involving impulsive and immediate responses, and refer to uncontrolled behaviors. While these behaviors are certainly annoying and harmful, they are less calculated compared to the use of devices for tracking a partner or blackmailing with intimate photos.

In contrast, primary psychopathy was a significant predictor of the use of devices and threatening to (or actually) post inappropriate, nude, or embarrassing photos of a partner as a combination of indirect, invasive, and direct forms of IPCV perpetration. This form of IPCV could be more damaging since it includes humiliation and an invasion of privacy. These behaviors could be further characterized by delayed IPCV actions, compared to, for example, excessive communication. This result is in line with previous studies that showed that among the Dark Triad traits, only psychopathy was a significant predictor of technology-facilitated sexual violence (Moor & Anderson, 2019). Furthermore, previous research found that both psychopathy and sadism were the only predictors of cyberaggression perpetration, including public humiliation, unwanted contact, and deception (Nocera et al., 2021), suggesting they have a role in the more harmful IPCV behaviors. The results of our study support the multidimensionality of psychopathy, showing there were different roles of psychopathy dimensions in the explanation of IPCV perpetration.

The results of the regression analysis also support the multidimensionality of narcissism. Narcissistic admiration showed a significant contribution to the explanation of threatening behaviors, while narcissistic rivalry to the explanation of checking behavior. Previous research found that among NARC components, narcissistic rivalry, as an antagonistic-oriented aspect of narcissism, was associated with negative outcomes of close relationships and revenge (Back et al., 2013) as well as with aggressive sexual behaviors (e.g., coercion and seduction, Barnett & Millward, 2021). Bearing this in mind, the associations between rivalry and checking behaviors could be explained by the combination of distrust of others, as one of the distinguishing characteristics of this narcissism dimension, and the entitlement as the central narcissism characteristic (Dinić et al., 2022). This could mean that people who have higher narcissism feel they have the right to monitor their partner's behavior as that partner is viewed as a possession. Our obtained result is in line with previous studies, which found that the antagonistic aspect of narcissism was related to toxic love styles, obsession, jealousy, and game-playing (Dinić &

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Jovanović, 2021) and dominance-based strategies to maintain romantic relationships (Zeigler-Hill et al., 2020). Thus, narcissistic rivalry is related to cyber, as well as to in-person, toxic relationship outcomes.

The results regarding the significant contribution of narcissistic admiration in the explanation of threatening behaviors needs further examination. Although previous research showed some positive short-term relationship outcomes in narcissistic admiration (Wrust et al., 2017), there is some evidence that narcissistic admiration correlates with perceived power in an intimate relationship, compared to narcissistic rivalry which showed no significant correlation (Vrabel et al., 2020). It could be that grandiosity, as the dominant characteristic of this dimension, and perceived power makes it easier for those with higher narcissistic admiration to threaten their partners and use this strategy to try to establish or maintain the dominance in a relationship.

Finally, in line with previous research (March et al., 2022), Machiavellianism showed the fewest number of significant correlations with IPCV and no significant predictions in the first step of the regression models. This is not surprising as those higher on Machiavellianism use aggression strategically and avoid direct aggression (Paulhus et al., 2008). Moreover, IPCV, unlike in-person IPV, can leave a permanent digital trace, thus keeping people high on Machiavellianism constrained of some IPCV forms, as they are hesitant to engage in behavior where their reputation could be ruined, or they could be exposed behaving negatively. In sum, **H1** is supported, with Machiavellianism showing the lowest associations with IPCV forms. **H2** is partially supported, depending on whether the total or partialized contributions were in question. Thus, narcissistic rivalry showed the highest correlations with most of the IPCV forms, but in the regression analysis, secondary psychopathy emerged as the strongest predictor. Since narcissistic rivalry refers to antagonism as the core of the dark traits (Dinić et al., 2023), it is possible that partialization would most affect this subtrait. Our results could be interpreted in the view of personality theories of IPV (e.g., Holtzworth-Munroe et al., 2000), suggesting there is a generally violent/antisocial type who is more prone to IPV and displays characteristics of higher dark traits, especially psychopathy. Therefore, the results show that this profile could also be found in IPCV and could contribute to a better understanding of nuanced personality characteristics of both men and women with a tendency towards IPCV.

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There were some gender differences in IPCV forms. Women engaged in more indirect, covert, and less trackable forms of IPCV (e.g., checking behaviors). One explanation of why women engage in indirect IPCV behaviors is these are less risky in terms of getting caught and facing direct confrontation or revenge. Also, considering gender roles, societal norms place more emphasis on women to manage and nurture relationships (e.g., O'Neil, 2013). This expectation can extend to the digital realm, where women may feel societal pressure to ensure the stability of their relationship by monitoring their partner's online behavior to protect the relationship from potential threats, such as infidelity or deceit. In contrast, men engaged more in high-risk, high-cost proactive behavior, more technologically demanding, and more invasive behaviors, captured by the CPI devices and photo subscale, in line with previous studies (Burke et al., 2011). Since gender roles often cast men as the dominant partners in relationships, it is possible that these expectations can manifest in a man's need to exert control and authority over their partner, leading to the use of technologically invasive methods like tracking devices. Our results could also be explained by higher technological skills in men in Serbia compared to women (Bradić-Martinović, 2022).

Considering these differences, our results confirmed the moderation role of gender in relation to some of the Dark Tetrad traits and IPCV forms. For example, in men, sadism was significantly associated with the use of devices and photos as well as with checking behaviors, which include privacy violations and invasive forms of violence. A possible explanation could be that, due to societal norms and expectations, women are often more admonished or criticized for their sexualization. Therefore, posting intimate photos without permission would likely be more harmful to women compared to men. Given that individuals with higher sadism are more inclined to perpetrate such harmful behavior, men with higher sadism may derive more enjoyment from the harm they cause, particularly considering the potentially more severe consequences for women, i.e., their current or ex partners. In addition, men are more prone to such harmful behaviors, and it could be assumed that if they have higher sadism, a trait particularly associated with deriving pleasure from hurting others (O'Meara et al., 2011), they would be even more prone to engage in these behaviors.

Although Machiavellianism was significantly related to threatening behaviors, this association was higher in men. In women, narcissistic rivalry was significantly associated with threatening behaviors. Both of these results could be explained in the context of gender roles. For

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men, being higher on dark traits and being more aggressive could be considered more socially accepted compared to women (e.g., O’Neil, 2013). While threatening behaviors, such as aggressive behavior, are also more acceptable in men, when women engage in behavior that is not in line with traditional women's gender roles or socially approved behavior, the predictors of that behavior were related to a more malevolent and socially toxic profile. In previous research, it was shown that aggression in women was related to various basic and dark traits compared to aggression in men (Dinić & Wertag, 2018). In the current research, the dominant trait in such a profile was the antagonistic aspect of narcissism, as the strategy was related to preventing social failure through self-defense. The obtained results in this study could also provide further insight into the motivation for threatening behaviors in both men and women. It appears that in men, these IPCV behaviors may serve as a means of manipulating a partner, while in women, they may be employed for ego protection. Unfortunately, the content of the threats is unknown; thus, it could be a threat of embarrassing or leaving the partner. Future studies should explore this issue to better understand the IPCV perpetration motivation among both men and women. In sum, **H3** is confirmed regarding the significance of gender role moderation, but the direction of the moderation is not fully established, suggesting different patterns of associations between specific dark traits and IPCV forms in men and women. These novel findings need more investigation.

Limitations

While this study provides some important insights into the risk factors of IPCV, a convenience sample in Serbia was used with the majority of participants being highly educated. Due to different methodology, we cannot compare the prevalence of IPCV between Serbia and other countries, but based on rough comparisons, it seems that the overall prevalence in our research was lower compared to previous research despite using the same measures in some of them (Borrajó et al., 2015; Brem et al., 2021; Burke et al., 2011; Cavalcanti & Coutinho, 2019; Fissel et al., 2021). However, due to a gap in the research on the prevalence of IPCV in Serbia, we cannot conclude whether the lower IPCV perpetration rates were due to differences in knowledge of technology, sociodemographic diversity, or potential cultural differences. Therefore, the generalizability of the results is limited to a population with a similar background with similar demographic characteristics. Measuring IPCV among the general population is essential to establish prevalence rates in a non-WEIRD sample (Henrich et al., 2010); however, it

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is unclear whether similar patterns of behavior would be found in forensic samples, such as sentenced IPCV offenders, and future research should compare different populations. In addition, the included measures were all self-reports, which can increase correlations between the measures due to a common method effect, and as with all cross-sectional designs, causation cannot be drawn from our findings. Although the data was collected anonymous, we cannot rule out the possibility that participants gave more socially desirable responses, which could indicate IPCV may be higher than what we found. Finally, it is possible that different patterns of predictors of IPCV could be found in same-sex relationships, and future research should investigate this.

Future Research Directions and Implications

As the measures were all self-reports, it would be advisable to include dyadic reports (from an actual partner) as well as reports on victimization to examine whether there is bidirectional IPCV among partners, and how the bidirectionality of the perpetration relates to dark traits. To expand the generalizability of the findings of the present study, future research could include cross-cultural and more socially diverse samples as well as forensic samples. Furthermore, future efforts could examine potential mechanisms underlying the associations between the dark traits and IPCV. From the standpoint of prevention strategies, it would be beneficial to explore whether characteristics from the domain of digital media use (e.g., excessive use of the internet or social media, see Duerksen, & Woodin, 2019 and Merlici et al., 2023) or characteristics that have been shown to be relevant for IPV, like self-regulation processes (e.g., affect dysregulation and negative urgency, Dugal et al., 2021), could be significant mediators in the associations between the dark traits and IPCV. In addition, future studies should include contextual factors (history of domestic violence, social norms, etc.) in exploring the associations between the dark traits and IPCV since these factors were found to be relevant for IPCV (e.g., Howell et al., 2016).

The results of the current study could inform prevention and evidence-based intervention programs targeting IPCV perpetration. The intervention programs should consider assessing for the Dark Tetrad traits since they emerged as risk factors for IPCV perpetration. On one hand, individualized treatment strategies that address perpetrators should include providing coping strategies based on the core traits. On the other hand, educating about dark traits could be viewed as a preventive strategy so that potential victims can better recognize these attributes in their partners. On an individual level, interventions should focus on understanding the psychological

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motivations behind cyberviolent behaviors, such as control, retaliation, or emotional manipulation. Effective prevention efforts could involve education on healthy relationship dynamics, digital literacy, and the ethical use of technology. Empowering individuals with skills to recognize and resist coercive behaviors online is essential. On a societal level, interventions should advocate for policy changes that protect victims, hold perpetrators accountable, and enhance digital privacy laws. For example, while some neighboring countries (such as Croatia and Montenegro) have enacted laws that classify the unauthorized sharing of intimate photos and videos as a criminal offense (colloquially called “revenge porn”), in Serbia, this remains unregulated. In addition, collaborating with technology companies to design platforms that prioritize user safety and privacy can also mitigate some risks.

Given the obtained gender differences, future prevention strategies may need to be tailored to men and women differently to address the different communication styles, expectations, and motivations, particularly with reference to women’s strategies of maintaining intimate relationships (e.g., March et al., 2023). Considering how technology is being used to control and humiliate partners, practitioners should incorporate awareness of IPCV in their practice. They may also benefit from consulting experts in the field of internet safety to provide advice and tools for victims of both IPCV and IPV.

Conclusion

Overall, we found that the frequency of IPCV was lower compared to other countries and cultures, but this does not make it negligible. The results of this study replicated, but also expanded on, previous research of the risk factors of specific IPCV forms. We found different patterns of associations between the Dark Tetrad traits and the different forms of IPCV, contributing to the multidimensional approach to both dark traits and IPCV. Furthermore, we found different patterns of associations between the dark traits and IPCV forms among men and women, highlighting that gender influenced IPCV behaviors differently. These results could better inform interventions, and future research could investigate these differences further, as it seems IPCV has reported higher rates than in-person IPV, highlighting that more people may be victims to this form of aggression and violence.

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The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

Notes on contributors

Bojana M. Dinić is an Associate Professor in Psychology at the Department of Psychology, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Novi Sad. Her research interests include the exploration of dark traits (e.g., psychopathy, narcissism, and antagonism) and their outcomes (e.g., aggression and violence) in both offline and online environments. Furthermore, her interests include psychometrics, and she has developed over 60 measures and adapted them to the Serbian language. She has been actively involved in numerous national and international projects, and she was the principal investigator for a national project focusing on online risky behaviors among adolescents.

ORCID 0000-0002-5492-2188

Danica Radosavljević finished her Master's degree in clinical psychology at the Department of Psychology, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Novi Sad, Serbia. Her research interests include dynamic of the intimate partner relationships, including the role of attachment styles in relationship satisfaction and quality, as well as personality predictors of various forms of intimate partner violence. She is employed as a commissioner at Department for Execution of Non-Institutional Sanctions and Measures at the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Serbia.

Christie Tetreault finished her PhD in psychology at the School of Psychology, National University of Ireland, Galway, Ireland (now University of Galway). She is a Post-doctoral

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Fellow for Centre for Forensic Behavioural Science and Justice Studies at the University of Saskatchewan, Canada. Her current research focusses on resilience and susceptibility to extremism. She also has research interests in forensic and social psychology with a special interest in cognitive processes in aggression and group dynamics.

ORCID 0000-0002-0453-2835

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Bojana M. Dinić: Conceptualisation; Methodology; Formal analysis; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing. Danica Radosavljević: Conceptualisation; Investigation; Writing – original draft. Christie Tetreault: Conceptualisation; Writing – review & editing.

Data access statement

The data are available from the corresponding author upon request.

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Table 1. Descriptives, Alpha Reliabilities, and Correlations ($N = 239$).

	Devices and photos	Excessive comm.	Threatening behaviors	Checking behaviors	M	PP	SP	NA	NR	S
Devices and photos	1									
Excessive comm.	.22	1								
Threatening behaviors	.28	.42	1							
Checking behaviors	.21	.30	.16	1						
M	.09	.07	.20	.17	1					
PP	.22	.17	.22	.13	.58	1				
SP	.16	.23	.25	.27	.47	.42	1			
NA	.09	.15	.21	.11	.19	.38	.08	1		
NR	.18	.22	.26	.32	.53	.55	.53	.47	1	
S	.20	.14	.22	.11	.52	.54	.46	.18	.55	1
<i>M</i>	1.02	1.34	1.04	1.53	2.69	1.93	2.38	3.24	1.99	1.50
<i>SD</i>	0.16	0.76	0.26	0.84	0.51	0.62	0.68	0.98	0.86	0.58
<i>Sk</i>	8.42	2.83	8.81	2.06	-	1.10	0.55	0.25	2.50	1.63
					0.03					
<i>Ku</i>	87.31	8.31	85.98	3.98	-	1.36	0.34	-	7.77	3.64
					0.21			0.27		
α	.67	.77	.80	.82	.717	.85	.73	.85	.84	.80

Note: M = Machiavellianism, PP = Primary psychopathy, SP = Secondary psychopathy, NA = Narcissistic admiration, NR = Narcissistic rivalry, S = Sadism. *M* and *SD* of raw average scores were presented, but correlations were calculated on normalized scores for all CPI scales, narcissistic rivalry, and sadism. *SE* for skewness (*Sk*) was .14, and for kurtosis (*Ku*) was .28. Correlations > .13 were significant at $p < .05$, and > .18 at $p < .001$.

Intimate Partner Cyberviolence and the Dark Tetrad

Table 2. Correlations Between Intimate Partner Cyberviolence Forms and Dark Tetrad Traits By Gender.

	Devices and photos		Excessive comm.		Threatening behaviors		Checking behaviors	
	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women
M	-.03	.16*	.07	.08	.26**	.18**	.17	.23**
PP	.12	.28***	.19	.18**	.25**	.22**	.22*	.18**
SP	.15	.19**	.15	.27***	.15	.31***	.37***	.22**
NA	.09	.09	.11	.17*	.19	.22**	.09	.12
NR	.16	.16*	.14	.29***	.11	.36***	.32***	.37***
S	.22*	.13	.18	.13	.25**	.21**	.31***	.07

Note: M = Machiavellianism, PP = Primary psychopathy, SP = Secondary psychopathy, NA = Narcissistic admiration, NR = Narcissistic rivalry, S = Sadism. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

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Table 3. Effects of Dark Tetrad Traits on Intimate Partner Cyberviolence Forms (Standardized Betas).

	Devices and photos	Excessive comm.	Threatening behaviors	Checking behaviors
M	-.12	-.14	.03	.03
PP	.18*	.07	.03	-.07
SP	.06	.19**	.17*	.17*
NA	-.01	.08	.15*	-.01
NR	.06	.13	.03	.31***
S	.10	.01	.08	-.12
R^2	.07**	.08***	.11***	.13***
SP		.18*	.16*	
NA			.15*	
Gender				.23***
ΔR^2	.01	.001	.00	.04***
M	-.31*			
NR			-.32*	.35***
S	.28*			
Gender	-1.22*			
Gender X M			-.89*	
Gender X			.41**	
NR				
Gender X S	-.23*			-.22*
ΔR^2	.03	.03	.06**	.03
Total R^2	.10**	.11**	.17***	.19***

Note: M = Machiavellianism, PP = Primary psychopathy, SP = Secondary psychopathy, NA = Narcissistic admiration, NR = Narcissistic rivalry, S = Sadism. For the clarity, in the 2nd and the 3rd steps, only significant contributions were presented. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

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Appendix

Table A. Frequencies and Percentages of the Responses to the Controlling Partners Inventory by Men and Women

	Men					Women				
	never	once	2 times	3 times	4 or more times	never	once	2 times	3 times	4 or more times
Checked sent/received email histories	81 (77.9)	12 (11.5)	4 (3.8)	1 (1)	6 (5.8)	132 (70.2)	22 (11.7)	15 (8)	4 (2.1)	15 (8)
Checked partner's cell call histories	84 (80.8)	12 (11.5)	2 (1.9)	3 (2.9)	3 (2.9)	122 (64.9)	27 (14.4)	18 (9.6)	3 (1.6)	18 (9.6)
Used partner's password to check-up on them	92 (88.5)	4 (3.8)	2 (1.9)	/	6 (5.8)	140 (74.5)	22 (11.7)	6 (3.2)	2 (1.1)	18 (9.6)
Sent threatening emails to partner	102 (98.1)	1 (1)	1 (1)	/	/	184 (97.9)	3 (1.6)	/	1 (0.5)	/
Made threatening cell calls to partner	102 (98.1)	2 (1.9)	/	/	/	186 (98.9)	/	1 (0.5)	/	1 (0.5)
Sent threatening text to partner	101 (97.1)	1 (1)	1 (1)	1 (1)	/	182 (96.8)	2 (1.1)	3 (1.6)	/	1 (0.5)
Sent excessive number of emails to partner	98 (94.2)	4 (3.8)	/	/	2 (1.9)	181 (96.3)	2 (1.1)	2 (1.1)	/	3 (1.6)
Made excessive number cell calls to partner	86 (82.7)	5 (4.8)	6 (5.8)	3 (2.9)	4 (3.8)	157 (83.5)	15 (8.0)	5 (2.7)	5 (2.7)	6 (3.2)
Sent excessive number of	79 (76)	13 (12.5)	5 (4.8)	/	7 (6.7)	139 (73.9)	20 (10.6)	9 (4.8)	5 (2.7)	15 (8.0)

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texts to partners										
Checked social network page to monitor partner	73 (70.2)	20 (19.2)	3 (2.9)	2 (1.9)	6 (5.8)	104 (55.3)	41 (21.8)	15 (8)	7 (3.7)	21 (11.2)
Checked partner's cell phone bill	95 (91.3)	6 (5.8)	/	1 (1)	2 (1.9)	177 (94.1)	5 (2.7)	2 (1.1)	/	4 (2.1)
Made embarrassing, insulting, threatening wall posts	104 (100)	/	/	/	/	185 (98.4)	2 (1.1)	1 (0.5)	/	/
Threatened to post inappropriate photos of partner	100 (96.2)	3 (2.9)	/	/	1 (1)	187 (99.5)	/	/	1 (0.5)	/
Posted inappropriate photos of partner	103 (99)	1 (1)	/	/	/	186 (98.9)	2 (1.1)	/	/	/
Used GPS etc. to monitor partner's location	97 (93.3)	1 (1)	2 (1.9)	/	4 (3.8)	185 (98.4)	1 (0.5)	1 (0.5)	/	1 (0.5)
Used Web cam to monitor partner's activities	104 (100)	/	/	/	/	187 (99.5)	1 (0.5)	/	/	/
Used hidden camera to monitor my partner's activities	101 (97.1)	3 (2.9)	/	/	/	186 (98.9)	2 (1.1)	/	/	/
Use spy ware to monitor my partner's activities	102 (98.1)	2 (1.9)	/	/	/	185 (98.4)	1 (0.5)	1 (0.5)		1 (0.5)

Note. Percentages within the gender are in parentheses.

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Table B

Descriptives of the Responses to the Controlling Partners Inventory Scores by Men and Women

	Men		Women	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Devices and photos	1.05	0.15	1.02	0.16
Excessive comm.	1.34	0.78	1.35	0.75
Threatening behaviors	1.04	0.20	1.04	0.29
Checking behaviors	1.35	0.73	1.62	0.88
Machiavellianism	2.80	0.46	2.62	0.52
Primary psychopathy	2.18	0.72	1.80	0.51
Secondary psychopathy	2.37	0.70	2.39	0.67
Narcissistic admiration	3.20	1.10	3.26	0.92
Narcissistic rivalry	2.20	1.04	1.86	0.71
Sadism	1.67	0.70	1.40	0.47

Note. *M* and *SD* of raw average scores were presented, but analyses were run on normalized scores for all CPI scales, narcissistic rivalry, and sadism.

Confirmatory factor analysis of Serbian adaptation of the CPI

Due to a violation of multivariate normality, a robust weighted least squares mean-adjusted estimator (WLSM) was used to test the original structure. The model fit was not satisfactory (WLSM $\chi^2_{(129)} = 310.97$, $p < .001$, CFI = .80, TLI = .76, RMSEA = .05). Item 11 (“checked partner’s cell phone bill”) showed nonsignificant loading on the first factor (.07) and based on its meaning and inter-item correlations, it showed the highest correlations with items from the fourth factor. It should be noted that in factor structure reported in Burke et al. (2011), this item was noticeably the lowest loading (.34) on the first factor, compared to the rest of the items. The modification indices (MI = 24.42) suggested that item 10 (“checked social network page to monitor partner”) should be moved from the second to the fourth factor. Moving both items to the fourth factor resulted in a good model fit (WLSM $\chi^2(129) = 169.63$, $p = .01$, CFI = .95, TLI = .94, RMSEA = .02). Both items referred to checking behavior in line with the content of the fourth factor.

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Table C

Parameters of the final model of the Serbian adaptatin of the Controlling Partners Inventory

Item	Standardized loading
Devices and photos	
CPI12	0.700
CPI13	0.581
CPI14	0.614
CPI15	0.304
CPI16	0.250
CPI17	0.789
CPI18	0.826
Excessive communication	
CPI7	0.472
CPI8	0.788
CPI9	0.958
Threatening	
CPI4	0.784
CPI5	0.541
CPI6	0.874
Checking behaviors	
CPI1	0.859
CPI2	0.850
CPI3	0.826
CPI11	0.298
CPI10	0.548

Table D

Correlations between factors

	1	2	3	4
1 Devices and photos	1			
2 Excessive communication	0.227	1		
3 Threatening	0.589	0.403	1	
4 Checking behaviors	0.159	0.359	0.088	1

Serbian adaptation of the CPI

Koliko često si ispoljavao/la sledeća ponašanja prema svom aktuelnom ili bivšem partneru?

1 = nikad, 5 = četiri ili više puta

CPI1 Proveravao/la njegove/njene poslate i primljene email-ove.

CPI2 Proveravao/la njegovu/njenu istoriju poziva na mobilnom telefonu.

CPI3 Koristio/la njegovu/njenu lozinku da bih ga proveravao.

CPI4 Slao/la mu/joj preteće email-ove.

CPI5 Upućivao/la mu/joj preteće pozive sa mobilnog telefona.

CPI6 Slao/la mu/joj preteće poruke.

CPI7 Slao/la mu/joj preveliki broj email-ova.

CPI8 Upućivao/la mu/joj preveliki broj poziva.

CPI9 Slao/la mu/joj preveliki broj poruka.

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CPI10 Proveravao/la njegove/njene stranice na društvenim mrežama da bih ga nadgledao/la.

CPI11 Proveravao/la njegov/njen račun za mobilni telefon.

CPI12 Postavljao/la posramljujuće, uvredljive, preteće objave na njegovoj/njenoj stranici na društvenim mrežama.

CPI13 Pretio/la da ću postaviti njegove/njene neprikladne slike javno ili dostupno drugima.

CPI14 Postavljao/la njegove/njene neprikladne slike javno ili dostupno drugima.

CPI15 Koristio/la GPS i slične uređaje da bih nadgledao/la gde se nalazi.

CPI16 Koristio/la web kameru da bih nadgledao/la šta radi.

CPI17 Koristio/la skrivenu kameru da bih nadgledao/la šta radi.

CPI18 Koristio/la poseban softver za praćenje njegovih/njenih aktivnosti na kompjuteru i/ili drugim uređajima.

Note. The scale can also be used in the context of a person's experience of being monitored by a partner, as well as for assessing how much the participant approves the above behaviors in an intimate, partner relationship.